

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ADEDEJI****FIRST NAME: SIMISOLA****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (MS Word - Office 365 for Mac)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Starting academic essay Writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-12)
2. Punctuation (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
3. Forms of writing languages (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
4. Style guides (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)
5. Latin abbreviations and expressions (EUCLID 2021, 58-64)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I have just concluded a review of the course package for period 1 of the ACA-401D course and what it entails. This course pack gives a basic overview of essay writing that meets international standards, especially written communication in the English language and the different forms it may take to present itself. I found it vital to the achievement of my goal because I am convinced that at the end of this course, I will not only learn to write essays properly but improve my writing skills as I advance in my career. This course equips me with basic concepts that will be useful in developing my response papers, research, and article writing.

In this response paper, I am discussing the process of starting essays and various structures of academic essays. Punctuations and how they differ across writing styles, guidelines for style guides, how to avoid plagiarism in academic essay writing and Latin abbreviations and expressions.

2) STARTING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

Most activities, if not all, take planning, for essays, planning starts with identifying the topic to be researched and being equipped with information that'd be used for the research. Having a plan for going about the essay is very important. This should include your initial thoughts and ideas about the research topic, which should constitute your preliminary essay plan that will help guide your research. "If an essay plan is written correctly, it will help you work out how you will answer the question and the type of information to use" (EUCLID 2021, 7). When planning, a topic of interest should have been implanted in the writer's mind to guide the whole essay writing. Reading and researching topics that are closely related to the question will give the knowledge and evidence to develop a possible hypothesis or answer the question (EUCLID 2021, 8).

After deciding the direction the essay will go using the already existing resources, the next step is to organize the information in order to make sense of it. An essay usually has a generic format of the introduction, body, and conclusion. To stay on course during the whole writing process, the question of the essay should always be in mind. "Don't lose sight of the focus of the essay. Remember, you have one purpose and one alone: to answer the question that has been set. Will the next sentence you write help to answer the question, or not? Apply this test to every sentence" (Eunson, Baden, 2012).

To prevent the risk of committing plagiarism, which is a serious academic offense, all cited information is meant to be referenced. It is important for an essay to have references and writers should adhere to referencing standards of the school or journal they are writing under (EUCLID 2021, 11). When turning in a paper there are some suggestions that will make the paper more interesting, staying focused, writing clearly, strongly discuss your point of view and do not plagiarize (EUCLID 2021, 13-14).

3) PUNCTUATION

My idea of a complete one-way communication is when the receiver of the information is able to decode and understand the information received in the same way the sender expects him or her to interpret the message. It is important to take into cognizance how information is being passed across with little or no complication so the receiver can understand the information from the point of view of the sender. Punctuations help to convey meanings to sentences (EUCLID 2021, 16). A particular sentence can convey two different meanings if punctuated differently. For instance, "Let's eat Grandma" and "Let's eat, Grandma" have different meanings (Digital Synopsis, n.d.).

There are different types of punctuation marks with different uses. Apostrophes help to show possession and indicate areas of contractions in words, Brackets help in indicating extra information, usually to the information that precedes it, and Bullet points are used to list words (EUCLID 2021, 16-18). The colon and semi-colon although similar, differ in their uses. They both connect two parts of a sentence, but the only difference is that the colon is used when the second sentence depends on the first and cannot stand alone

as a complete sentence but when the second statement can stand alone as a complete sentence, the semicolon is used (EUCLID 2021, 18). Commas have multiple uses: they can be used to add a description to a sentence or separate items in a sentence to mention a few (EUCLID 2021, 19-20).

4) FORMS OF WRITING LANGUAGES

EUCLID (2021, 25) explores the two major forms of World English which are British and American English, and the American variant is said to have gained international significance over the other due to some factors. These two major forms of World English have both similarities and differences. Some words may have different pronunciations with the same spellings and vice-versa. Further, some words may be the same spelling but may convey additional meanings when used in some contexts. Other differences include the usage of punctuation, collective nouns, and plural adjectives.

As a Nigerian National, with my country colonized by the British, over time, I have found it really easy to write using British English but while growing up, I was exposed to American English through movies and books, and I learned how to pronounce or spell some English words differently which I have consistently used over the years in my academics and career life. However, learning and relearning is a constant process.

I have learned that when writing an essay, a writer should remember to choose what writing language is to be used for the essay. EUCLID (2021, 25) proposes that when a writing language is chosen for an essay, the writer is expected to follow through with the said writing language to ensure consistency and uniformity.

5) STYLE GUIDES

Style guides adopt a set of rules or standards to enforce consistency in academic essays (Oxford University, 2014). A style guide is implemented to ensure coherence with completed publications, and authors under a body, for instance, a school, or media house (EUCLID 2021, 41). Style guides come with a predetermined format; EUCLID uses the Turabian style and American English although, British English is also acceptable (EUCLID 2021, 41). This is to ensure that all papers that are published by the school carry the style of the school and promotes uniformity. The style guides ensure consistency in the use of fonts, spelling, abbreviations, structure, headings, and trademarking to mention a few (EUCLID 2021, 41).

Leading up to this moment, the only style of writing and referencing I learned was the American Psychological Association (APA) style guide for writing academic essays. I learned that it was a generally acceptable writing style for writers in the health field and is widely known across the world. Now, trying to learn how to write using the Turabian style has been interesting, and I am hopeful that before the end of my DIPH, I would have been able to write fluently using the Turabian style.

6) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

Walden University describes Latin abbreviations as “an effective way to use common argumentative phrases in parenthetical material without taking up much space or distracting your readers from the main ideas of your sentences” (Walden University, n.d.). When writing formally, the English translations of the Latin abbreviations should be used (Walden University, n.d.; EUCLID 2021, 59).

While writing this response paper, I had initially used the Latin abbreviation “i.e.” which means that is and I didn’t know that it wasn’t acceptable when writing formally. The use of plain English language is advised when writing formally to provide any reader ease in understanding.

There are a lot of Latin abbreviations that are currently in use such as e.g. which means for example, i.e. which means that is, etc. which means and so on, N.B. which means note well, and so on (EUCLID 2021, 59-60). They can be used when writing informally or when writers want to reduce the number of words written. It is best to use the abbreviations that are widely known

7) CONCLUSION

Writing academic essays is not the same as informal writing. There are sets of rules and guides writers must follow in order to deem the paper acceptable. I have been able to understand that different organizations, companies, or schools have different guidelines for writing, and as a new student of EUCLID, with the Turabian writing style, I have to learn how to write plainly and coherently using the acceptable format and, in the process, improve on my vocabulary, writing skills and become a professional in the Turabian writing style. I have also learned the dangers of plagiarism and how to cite an author or a paper.

This period is an interesting way to start my Ph.D. in International Public Health because I have been able to learn, unlearn and relearn many things in terms of writing and I look forward to proceeding in this course and improving myself as time goes by.

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